

Premise

Firstly, our view of violence emphasizes harm to persons rather than property, as punishment against property damage is so often used as a tool of oppression in times of political crisis. It also focuses on physical violence, though it recognizes that psychological and other types of violence can create problems in legitimizing civil resistance.

Research Question

The main question is whether civil violence should be deemed legitimate, lawful, even when it leads to civil war (or a non-international conflict, as termed under the framework of international humanitarian law provided by the Geneva Convention).

Research Design

The research requires an empirical, positivist framework that rests on qualitative data analysis. The research should be conducted applying the concept of triangulation, which combines different methods (exploratory, descriptive, and analytical) and fits qualitative studies. To proceed with the debate, the Working Group (WG) on Civil Violence suggests, first, to analyze the theoretical elements, definitions, and current research, then to consider some cases from which to infer theoretical insights, and, eventually, to come up with hypotheses and generate a theory. Case studies will be nested in the broader discussion about civil violence. The research should scrutinise the phenomenon of civil violence starting from an analysis based on three pillars: 1) exploratory-descriptive; 2) theoretical-conceptual; 3) legal-ethical. To overcome the possibility of bias, which is the main challenge in interpretive studies such as this, the WG suggests examining all the pertinent theoretical positions before interpreting data in order to ensure theoretical sensitivity and preparedness for the emergence of conflicting information.

Findings and Future Research Directions

The WG believes that legitimate civil violence is a viable concept, with existing international law providing a useful starting point. These laws delineate legitimate political violence as that which is used as a last resort against systematic threat to fundamental rights, such as the right to life. It should be a last resort, not only for the immediate harm involved, but because it so easily creates a hostile environment for the construction of viable democratic institutions.

However, the WG recognizes that this concept leaves much room for further debate. For example, it is possible to argue whether social and economic rights can be considered fundamental rights. While civil and political rights are much easier to define and measure, social and economic rights should not be disregarded.

Furthermore, it is possible to view instances of civil violence along a spectrum, instead of the binary ‘legitimate vs. illegitimate’. This concept would help nuancing the perspective of international law, and possible criteria for judging incidences of civil violence could include: the perpetrator’s options for non-violent resistance, the goal of the action of violence, and the proportionality of violence according to the perpetrator’s available options. In general, violence committed by people and groups with fewer political options has a greater claim to legitimacy. Violence committed by more powerful people in the name of the very vulnerable may constitute a special case, assuming that it was done in genuine solidarity and dialogue with the people whose rights it claims to protect.

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